

cessda

Roadshow

Series | 30 September
8 - 14 - 21 - 28 October

2021

Follow us

@CESSDA_Data

linkedin.com/company/cessda

The CESSDA[®] Roadshow 2021 Programme Committee

The CESSDA[®] Roadshow Programme Committee was made up of representatives from the CESSDA[®] main office, Service Providers and the Training Community. They were supported by Trust-IT Services.

Ron Dekker
CESSDA[®] Director

Eleanor Smith
CESSDA[®] Senior
Communication Officer

Irena Vipavc Brvar
Head of Department
Social Sciences Data
Archives, University of
Ljubljana

Catherine Slaatta
CESSDA[®] Communication
Officer

Ilona Trtíková

Data Services Manager at
The Czech Social Science
Data Archive (ČSDA) at
the Institute of Sociology
ASCR

Kristi Winters

GESIS, CESSDA®
Communication support
2021

Jindřich Krejčí

is the director of the
Institute of Sociology of
the Czech Academy of
Science.

John Shepherdson

CESSDA® Cloud Platform
Delivery Director

The full team was supported by Trust-IT Services

 Trust-IT Services
communicating to markets

The CESSDA[®] Roadshow Series

In a world beset by challenges, from the COVID-19 pandemic to climate change, the social sciences have never been more important for impartial, evidence-based research and analysis. The CESSDA[®] Roadshow series explored global research challenges from COVID-19, migration to climate change, cancer and chronic diseases and recycling.

The Roadshows placed centre stage two CESSDA[®] services that are essential support for research in the social sciences: the Data Catalogue ([CESSDA DC[®]](#)) and the Data Management Expert Guide ([CESSDA DMEG[®]](#))

Designed with practicality in mind, they shared advice and insights from both national service providers and researchers to help the community and newcomers navigate their way through datasets and manage their data plans in the best possible way, showing how data is being reused and shared.

The CESSDA[®] Roadshow series took place on the following dates:

1

**CESSDA[®]
and COVID-19**

on 30.09.2021

2

**CESSDA[®]
and Migration**

on 08.10.2021

3

**CESSDA[®]
and Climate
Change**

on 14.10.2021

4

**CESSDA[®]
and Cancer
and Chronic
Diseases**

on 21.10.2021

5

**CESSDA[®]
and Circular
Economy**

on 28.10.2021

The Roadshow's Impact in numbers

The audience engaged

Attendees came from all over the globe

We asked attendees if they had used the CESSDA DC® or CESSDA DMEG® previously for their research

Have you used the CESSDA Data Catalogue for your research?

● Yes ● No

Have you used the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide?

● Yes ● No

CESSDA[®] Roadshow on COVID-19

Panellists

Alle Bloom
UK Data Service

Ricarda Braukmann
DANS

Otto Bodi
AUSSDA

Julia P. Rechteck
University of Vienna

Helena Laaksonen
CESSDA COVID-19
ambassador

Anna Zamberlan

Filippo Gioachin

Davide Gritti

University of Trento

Giulia Malaguarnera
Eurodoc

The CESSDA® Roadshow series kicked off with a deep dive on COVID-19 on 30 September 2021, highlighting cross-national datasets and surveys in the Data Catalogue (CESSDA DC®) with a practical guide and demo on how to discover them.

Designed as a practical deep dive, the CESSDA® Roadshow on COVID-19 brought together researchers and service providers on how to use and re-use the reservoir of CESSDA® COVID-19 resources for the social sciences, such as national data archives, surveys and gender-related studies. Participants were shown real-world examples of fast-track

publication and collaboration.

Presentations on the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide® gave a practical guide on data discovery, archiving and publishing routes, as well as European diversity. Interactive discussions brought insights into societal impacts from the CESSDA® COVID-19 Ambassador, Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers. The event wrapped-up with more interactive discussions on how CESSDA® and its service providers are supporting researchers on global challenges.

Main takeaways

- ◆ The CESSDA DC[®] is a treasure trove for the social sciences with over 30,000 datasets available. 2020 marked a major milestone with the inclusion of COVID-19 datasets and metadata from national data archives, surveys, administrative and government data and gender-related studies as new entries from 13 national service providers. Collectively, these datasets bring multiple insights into the many societal impacts ripe for investigation, reuse and citation in the social sciences.
- ◆ The data available has enabled research on behavioural aspects during the pandemic, such as impacts on employment and the division of domestic chores over time. The surveys have a broad scope at the intersection of diverse disciplines, from economics to psychology, bringing insights into behaviour previously not covered or not given so much weight as is the case with the pandemic, revealing just how important it is. Research has also brought new insights into the role of open science in disciplines like the social sciences, with a focus on transparency and openness, citizen reactions versus policy decisions, where data needs to be anonymised to protect privacy.
- ◆ The pandemic is generating a lot of new data, which has to be archived very quickly and so has increased the workload but has also led to new data collections. AUSSDA has also set up a new workflow for fast-track publishing, which could be extended to other research themes. AUSSDA has also implemented a set of security checks for staff working from home and has also led to more structured and efficient meetings with more inclusive discussions. In Finland, the demand for data at the Social Science Data Archive has skyrocketed and this trend continues in 2021 though it remains to see what changes may occur in the future. Like Austria, the shift to remote working was very swift with positive attitudes towards carrying out many tasks remotely provided the network and IT system are properly protected. This is unlikely to change in the future though there is also the need for CESSDA[®] members to meet physically in what is a concerted effort.
- ◆ Calls to actions:
 - ◆ **Alle Bloom, UK Data Service:**
Make the most of the wealth that CESSDA[®] has to offer, including secondary sources.
 - ◆ **Anna Zamberlan, University of Trento:**
There is a lot of untapped potential to explore more general sociological topics from the precise and descriptive accounts already available.
 - ◆ **Julia Partheymüller, Austrian Corona Panel Project:**
Speed up the time to make the data available so new research papers can go through peer review as the most legitimate source of knowledge so publications keep pace with an evolving pandemic.
 - ◆ **Helena Laaksonen, Chair of CESSDA[®] General Assembly and Director of the Finnish Social Science Data Archive:**
Use the DMEG to archive and publish data so it is preserved as a knowledge base for when the next pandemic occurs.
 - ◆ **Otto Bodi-Fernandez, AUSSDA:**
Think about data sharing not at the end of a project but early on so it is available to others for reuse.
 - ◆ **Riccarda Braukmann, DANS:**
National service providers are here to help so researchers should get in touch if they haven't already done so.

Training material

[Download the slides for reuse](#)

Download the [CESSDA Behavioural Data for COVID-19 research](#) booklet, presented at ICRI2021

Reuse the recordings in your trainings

[Welcome and Overview of the Roadshow](#), Marieke Willems & Stephanie Parker, Trust-IT on behalf of CESSDA®

[Places to find COVID data and what data is available & Demo on how to search the CESSDA DC®](#), Alle Bloom, UK Data Service

[CESSDA DMEG® - Data Discovery, Archiving and Publication Routes](#), European Diversity, Ricarda Braukmann, DANS

[How CESSDA DMEG® supports publication in the social sciences](#), Otto Bodi, AUSSDA

User stories for inspiration

Julia P. Rechteck

University of Vienna

Data production and re-use of datasets, Julia Partheymüller, University of Vienna
The Austrian Corona Panel Project uses the fast track publication route provided by the Austrian Social Science Data Archive.

- ◊ [Watch the recorded story](#)
- ◊ Listen to the [CESSDA®podcast with Sylvia Kritzinger from the Austrian Corona Panel Project](#)
- ◊ Dive into the story yourself. [The Austrian Corona Panel Project: monitoring individual and societal dynamics amidst the COVID-19 crisis](#)

University of Trento

Anna Zamberlan Filippo Gioachin Davide Gritti

Work less, help out more? The persistence of gender inequality in housework and childcare during UK COVID-19 - Zamberlan et al. Anna Zamberlan, Filippo Gioachin, Davide Gritti, University of Trento.

Research performed with data available in the UK Data Archive, and discoverable via the CESSDA DC®

- ◊ [Watch the recorded story](#)
- ◊ [Dive into the story yourself](#)

CESSDA[®] Service providers and researchers discuss the CESSDA DC[®] and CESSDA DMEG[®]

Alle Bloom

UK Data Service

Ricarda Braukmann

DANS

Otto Bodi

AUSSDA

Julia P. Rechteck

University of Vienna

Helena Laaksonen

CESSDA COVID-19
Ambassador

Giulia Malaguarnera

Eurodoc

Anna Zamberlan

Filippo Gioachin

Davide Gritti

University of Trento

- ◆ [Interactive panel discussion on COVID-19 data discovery with Helena Laaksonen \(TUNI\) and Giulia Malaguarnera \(Eurodoc\)](#)
- ◆ [Interactive discussion the societal impacts of COVID-19 dataset, reuse and fast-track publication with all panelists](#)

CESSDA[®] Roadshow #2 on Migration

Panellists

Ami Saji

Sciences Po

Dimitra Kondyli

EKKE

Peter Čerče

KZS

Dimitri Prandner

Johannes Kepler University

Ahmed Wali

HumMingBird project

Meredith Winn

Sciences Po

With approximately 281 million people, or 3.6 % of the world's population, currently living outside their country of birth, migration policies need to be based on reliable and impartial evidence.

CESSDA[®] offers a wealth of resources for researchers, enabling them to use and reuse datasets and define their data management plan. The focus of this Roadshow was to talk participants through the wonderful world of data, giving practical tips and sharing first-hand experiences through researcher and service provider viewpoints. The overall goal was to show how data and human resources combine to help the societies we live in become more inclusive so they can thrive on diversity.

The CESSDA DC[®] has over 3,000 datasets on migration and minorities, searchable and documented in 14 European languages with rich metadata that facilitates cross-disciplinary research all from a single access point. This CESSDA[®] Roadshow shares insights into the treasure trove of datasets in the CESSDA Data Catalogue[®] for social science research on migration. Service providers and researchers give practical tips on using the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide[®], especially when dealing with such highly sensitive data. Interactive discussions with panellists and opportunities for participants to share their viewpoints are key features of the Roadshow.

Main takeaways

- ◆ CESSDA® datasets enable quality and transparent research as core values the social sciences bring to the public debate on migration.
- ◆ Migration is an excellent example of a global challenge where research findings, such as comparisons between policy and scientific data can be used to inform policymakers and civil society activists outside the core CESSDA® community.
- ◆ The community of CESSDA® service providers is instrumental in connecting researchers carrying out research at both national and cross-national levels, helping them also deal with sensitive data through the good practices in the DMEG.
- ◆ Several services providers have also played a key role in ensuring that the EMM Survey Registry is interoperable with well-structured metadata and based on recommended standards, thereby maximising its usability. This is just one example of how connecting the service providers with the research community helps save time and build economies of scale.
- ◆ The European Language Thesaurus is another important tool for using and reusing the datasets, helping researchers navigate diverse terms and concepts related to the datasets and conduct their research based on common understandings.

Training material

[Download the slides for reuse](#)

[Tune in on the **CESSDA[®]** podcast on migration and mobility here](#)

Dimitra Kondyli

EKKE

Reuse the recordings in your trainings

[Welcome and Overview of the Roadshow,](#)
Marieke Willems & Stephanie Parker, Trust-IT
on behalf of CESSDA[®]

[CESSDA Data Catalogue[®] for Migration and Discovery,](#) Dimitra Kondyli, EKKE

User stories for inspiration

Peter Čerče

KZS

[CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide® & Data Catalogue® for Users](#), Peter Cerce, Head of the Centre for IT and Infrastructural Support to Research at the Science and Research Centre Koper and its Research Library

Dimitri Prandner

Johannes Kepler University

[Migrant Minorities and Survey Research. Reusing the EMM Survey Registry](#). Dimitri Prandner, Johannes Kepler University

Ami Saji

Sciences Po

[Ethnic and Migrant Minority Survey Registry & CESSDA Data Catalogue® for Discovery](#), Ami Saji, SciencesPo & SSHOC

Meredith Winn

Sciences Po

[Ethnic & Migrant Minority Question Databank. Reusing the EMM Survey Registry](#), Meredith Winn, SciencesPo

Ahmed Wali

HumMingBird project

[Challenges in international migration statistics](#). Ahmed Wali, HumMingBird project

CESSDA[®] Service providers and researchers discuss the CESSDA DC[®] and CESSDA DMEG[®]

Panellists

Ami Saji
Sciences Po

Dimitra Kondyli
EKKE

Peter Čerče
KZS

Dimitri Prandner
Johannes Kepler University

Ahmed Wali
HumMingBird project

Meredith Winn
Sciences Po

[!\[\]\(04abccf04933d76a5e2e7252f1218f84_img.jpg\) CESSDA[®] Roadshow on migration interactive discussion](#)

CESSDA[®] Roadshow #3 on Climate Change

Panellists

Tuomas J. Alaterä

FSD

Patrícia Miranda

APIS Archive

Luís Junqueira

University of Lisboa

Vasco Ramos

University of Lisboa

Harri Melin

Tampere University

This CESSDA® Roadshow on 14 October 2021 from 14:00-15:30 CEST was a deep dive on climate change research in the social sciences, which are key to ensuring impartial, reliable and trusted datasets contribute to tackling this global challenge.

Bringing together CESSDA® experts and users, the Roadshow zoomed in on datasets available in the Finnish Social Science Data Archive as just one example of the wealth of resources available to researchers in the CESSDA Data Catalogue®. Experts also gave practical guides on the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide®. Researchers then shared their first-

hand experiences in using the CESSDA Data Catalogue® and reusing data from related studies, highlighting benefits also for cross-disciplinary research. These flash talks served as a springboard for the interactive discussions with invited panelists and participants, sharing diverse viewpoints as data service providers and members of the social sciences community in the context of CESSDA®.

Main takeaways

- ◆ It is essential that research on climate change reaches a wider audience, such as decision makers and the private sector, including small companies that can benefit from the data available. CESSDA® members can bring value by making these connections.
- ◆ Having more data and more reliable data on climate change is critical for enabling new research and distributing it across all relevant stakeholders, where CESSDA® has the opportunity to engage with a much wider audience.
- ◆ Data quality is key for both cross-disciplinary and comparative cross-national research because we need data based on worldwide knowledge for research on this global challenge. In this respect, comparative studies are fundamentally important.
- ◆ Metadata deposits are much easier to re-use as it sets researchers on the right track, leveraging the solid support of the national service providers. Service provider support is an essential part of the research workflow. For example, APIS has enabled researchers to find relevant data and metadata for their studies, but beyond this, they help prepare them for the road ahead, highlighting the importance of open data, how the various procedures work, ensuring they have controlled vocabularies at hand so the research can be conducted in a very detailed manner. This is a circular process from start to finish, ensuring data is findable and accessible to others so they can benefit from it.
- ◆ CESSDA® has come up trumps with the CESSDA DMEG® as it really supports the research workflow from discovery to publication. Hence, this is all part of the CESSDA DMEG® journey, starting with discovery, and the end-to-end researcher experience through the entire data lifecycle in well-organised chapters with questions to check understanding around data management plans.
- ◆ To reuse data, it needs to be published. Researchers can easily tap into the CESSDA DMEG® questions on publishing and archiving through trusted repositories like CESSDA®. Researchers must properly cite data, to sources and original authors to maximise the impacts of data dissemination through the correct attributions.

Training material

[Download the slides for reuse](#)

Reuse the recordings in your trainings

[Welcome and Overview of the Roadshow](#),
Marieke Willems & Stephanie Parker, Trust-IT on behalf of CESSDA®

[CESSDA DC® for Climate Change: An overview of Datasets in Finnish and English Datasets for Discovery](#),
Tuomas J. Alaterä, FSD

[CESSDA DMEG® on Archive & Publish](#),
Patrícia Miranda, APIS Archive

User stories for inspiration

Luís Junqueira

University of Lisboa

[CESSDA® User story on the importance of publishing data and organizing \(meta\)data](#), Luís Junqueira, University of Lisboa

Vasco Ramos

University of Lisboa

[CESSDA® User Story on the importance and the benefits of reuse of data in cross-disciplinary research](#), Vasco Ramos, University of Lisboa

Harri Melin

Tampere University

[A CESSDA DC® User story, insights from Finland](#) by Harri Melin, Tampere University

CESSDA[®] Service providers and researchers discuss the CESSDA DC[®] and CESSDA DMEG[®]

Panelists

Tuomas J. Alaterä
FSD

Patrícia Miranda
APIS Archive

Luís Junqueira
University of Lisboa

Vasco Ramos
University of Lisboa

Harri Melin
Tampere University

◊ [Watch the CESSDA Roadshow on climate change interactive discussion](#)

CESSDA® Roadshow #4 on Cancer and Major Chronic Diseases

Panellists

Alle Bloom

UK Data Service

Beate Lichtwardt

Gry Henriksen

Norwegian Centre
for Research Data

Patty Doran

University of Manchester

Nasir Raja

Danielle Freitas Gomes

Karen Dennison

University College London

This CESSDA[®] Roadshow focused on how the CESSDA DC[®] and DMEG[®] support researchers in their work on cancer and major chronic diseases based on impartial and trusted datasets and metadata. It featured a practical demo of the DC and highlighted the importance of secure access to data, storage and protection, with real-world examples of best practices for use and reuse by the social sciences research community. Participants could also enjoy an engaging interactive discussion between the service providers and researchers on the roadshow topic.

Main takeaways

- ◊ Combining social data with administrative data reveals key trends about cancer and other chronic diseases, enabling much deeper insights while also saving money. There is a huge potential to conduct research on many different variables, such as emotional support, with a wealth of data in social surveys showing how people are really affected by cancer and other health conditions in both the short and long terms.
- ◊ Researchers need access to high-quality data on diverse facets of healthcare, including comparisons across countries. Trusted archives enable researchers to easily discover the data, interrogate it and use it. This in turn helps generate evidence-based research at national and international level, also in terms of enabling informed decision making from a policy standpoint.
- ◊ Service provider support plays a central role as they have in-depth knowledge about their data, which has a practical value, but can also support researchers with best practices on data management, including GDPR compliance. There are also other ways where service providers can assist, such as dealing with data in different formats and applying for secure data access on top of all the training resources available.
- ◊ Interconnecting researchers is also important as it allows them to discover all other datasets that could yield insights, unleashing the potential for new datasets to enrich investigations. It is important to keep highlighting the wealth of data available.

Training material

[Download the slides for reuse](#)

Reuse the recordings in your trainings

[Welcome and Overview of the Roadshow,](#)
Marieke Willems & Stephanie Parker, Trust-IT on behalf of CESSDA®

[CESSDA Data Catalogue® - Discovery at national and European levels,](#) Alle Bloom, UK Data Service

[Store and Protect with the CESSDA Data Management Guide®,](#) Gry-Hege Henriksen, Norwegian Centre for Research Data (NSD)

User stories for inspiration

Patty Doran

University of Manchester

[Resilience and living well beyond cancer: the relationship between emotional support and quality of life](#), Patty Doran, University of Manchester

University College London

Danielle Freitas Gomes

Karen Dennison

Nasir Raja

[Use case on Center for Longitudinal Studies - how to store and how to protect](#), Danielle Freitas Gomes, Karen Dennison and Nasir Raja, University College London

Beate Lichtwardt

UK Data Service

[Use case on The Five Safes framework for accessing sensitive data via the SecureLab at UK Data Service](#), Beate Lichtwardt, UK Data Service

CESSDA[®] Service providers and researchers discuss the CESSDA DC[®] and CESSDA DMEG[®]

Panelists

Alle Bloom

UK Data Service

Beate Lichtwardt

Gry Henriksen

Norwegian Centre for Research Data

Patty Doran

University of Manchester

Nasir Raja

Danielle Freitas Gomes

Karen Dennison

University College London

[Watch the CESSDA[®] Roadshow on cancer and major chronic diseases interactive discussion](#)

CESSDA[®] Roadshow #5 on Circular Economy

Panelists

Jan Dalstent

Danish National Archives

Konstantinos Tsagarakis

Technical University of Crete

Johana Chylíková

Czech Social Science Data Archive

Ana Slavec

InnoRenew CoE

This CESSDA® Roadshow on the Circular Economy brought together experts from service providers and top-level researchers to explore the key role of the social sciences underpinned by impartial, reliable data on attitudes and practices related to recycling and eco-design.

Demos and deep dives guided participants through valuable resources in the CESSDA Data Catalogue®, with examples of data use and reuse as well as best practices on how researchers can organise and process data using the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide®.

Lively interactive discussions shed light on key opportunities for CESSDA® to be at the forefront of an interdisciplinary approach to research on the circular economy and help build the large body of knowledge we need moving forward.

Main takeaways

- ◆ Interdisciplinary cooperation is a key aspect for the circular economy, starting before data collection with consensus on definitions, new terminology and formulating questions with a view to collecting the most informative data possible.
- ◆ CESSDA[®] is making an important contribution to research in the social sciences through its data and metadata collection, shedding light on people's attitudes towards recycling as an environmental good practice, including self-reported behaviour.
- ◆ The CESSDA[®] archives can themselves be seen as reflecting circular economy principles by preserving data created for reuse so others can “recycle” it and benefit from insights already made. This is also effective in reducing the amount of time spent collecting data by optimising data sources that already exist.
- ◆ What would be useful are datasets that help us understand if there are gaps between attitudes and reported behaviour as opposed to what actually happens. Decisions made by enterprises can also have a significant impact so this also needs to be assessed, for example, understanding business motivations and consumer reactions. This would make the CESSDA[®] contribution even better. Surveys combined with government data can both help research on the circular economy.
- ◆ Concerted efforts are also important for enhancing the metadata from national statistical offices and making it available to a wider pool of researchers. Equally important are the use cases like the ones emerging from the Roadshow series. They are also an important channel for others to get inspiration and learn from the experiences of other researchers. CESSDA[®] is very well placed to be at the forefront of cooperation and interdisciplinary approaches to research on the circular economy.

Training material

[Download the slides for reuse](#)

Reuse the recordings in your trainings

[Welcome and Overview of the Roadshow,](#)
Marieke Willems & Stephanie Parker, Trust-IT on behalf of CESSDA®

[CESSDA Data Catalogue® - Discovery of Danish Datasets related to the Circular Economy,](#) Jan Dalsten, Danish National Archives

[Data Management Expert Guide® - Organise & Process,](#) Johana Chyliková, Czech Social Science Data Archive (CSDA)

User stories for inspiration

Konstantinos Tsagarakis

Technical University of Crete

[Use case on Circular Economy Research - A view on societal impacts and priorities](#)
Konstantinos Tsagarakis, Professor of Economics of Environmental Science and Technology at the Technical University of Crete.

Ana Slavec

InnoRenew CoE

[Challenges with the reuse of data on circular economy: Experience of researchers at the InnoRenew CoE](#), Ana Slavec, InnoRenew CoE Renewable Materials and Healthy Environments Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence.

[!\[\]\(422c27341a8956ddd0f356d697046fbd_img.jpg\) Dive into Ana's story](#)

CESSDA[®] Service providers and researchers discuss the CESSDA DC[®] and CESSDA DMEG[®]

Panellists

Jan Dalstent
Danish National Archives

Konstantinos Tsagarakis
Technical University of Crete

Johana Chyliková
Czech Social Science Data Archive

Ana Slavec
InnoRenew CoE

[◆ Watch the CESSDA[®] Roadshow on circular economy interactive discussion](#)

The CESSDA[®] Roadshow basis, conclusions and next steps

This roadshow series fostered the reuse of a set of promotional materials for researchers designed to raise awareness on the CESSDA DC[®] and CESSDA DMEG[®]. We list them here by CESSDA[®] Service Providers.

[CESSDA DC[®] Podcasts for Data Discovery](#)

CESSDA DC[®] for research on Migration and Mobility

Ami Saji

Junior researcher at the Centre of European and Comparative Politics at SciencePo in France and Social Sciences and Humanities open Cloud (SSHOC)

In terms of helping to tackle global challenges, the value of the datasets is something that really resonates with ethnic and migration studies data community. This is why we're generating such rich metadata about the surveys, which really bring meaningful insights from the research done.

CESSDA DC® for research on COVID-19

Sylvia Kritzinger

Professor at the University of Vienna and principal investigators of the Austrian National Election Study (AUTNES) and the Austrian Corona Panel Project (ACPP)

All disciplines can really benefit from these datasets because they can find indicators, theoretical variables, and combine them for other disciplines.

CESSDA DC® for research on European Values

Ruud Luijkx

Associate professor at the department of Sociology of Tilburg University and chair of the Methodology Group of European Values Studies

The data that the European Values Study has made available through the CESSDA Data Catalogue are used in thousands of publications and is the joint core dataset created in collaboration with the World Values Study.

CESSDA DC® for research on Election Studies

Georg Lutz

FORS Director and professor of political science at the University of Lausanne

The data FORS has made available through the CESSDA Data Catalogue will help policy makers to understand what drives people in their political choices and also provide general insights on human behaviour.

CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide User Story

Ana Slavec, PhD in Statistics, used chapter 5 “protect” on **data protection** for her work with personal data.

➤ The Researcher

Ana Slavec - Consulting Statistician at InnoRenew CoE

In 2016, I obtained a PhD in Statistics from the Faculty of Social Sciences at the University of Ljubljana where I was a research assistant, first at the Centre for Social Informatics and later at the [Slovenian Social Science Data Archives](#). I am currently employed as a consulting statistician and postdoctoral researcher at the [InnoRenew CoE](#) Renewable Materials and Healthy Environments Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence, an independent research institute established in 2017, that focuses mainly on research in wood modification and restorative environmental and ergonomic design.

➤ My research project.

In [my postdoctoral project](#) I am studying the use of survey questionnaires used to study **human patterns of behaviour within the built environment to improve occupant well-being**.

The objective of the project is to identify the existing measurement instruments used by architects and building researchers to collect and understand the needs of building users in the design process and in post-occupancy evaluations, assess the validity and comprehensibility of existing instruments and then design and assess improved survey questionnaires.

In the first phase, the project includes a literature review of relevant works that use surveys or other social science research methods to study building users, a collection of examples of survey questions, and focus groups with architects and building researchers. In the second phase, **survey questions will be selected for evaluation with quantitative and qualitative questionnaire pre-testing methods**.

InnoRenew CoE is performing research on the **development of materials for a circular economy, which is one of the critical European and Global challenges**. By providing more accurate data on user behaviour and attitudes of building users, my postdoctoral project will contribute to making buildings more sustainable.

➤ My use of the CESSDA DMEG

I learned about CESSDA when working at the [Slovenian Social Science Data Archive](#). I came across the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide when I was preparing a data [management plan for my postdoctoral project](#) and used it to plan my use of data. I read several chapters but the most useful one was the one on **data protection** which is of crucial importance when working with personal data. In particular, I valued tips on how to process personal data, how to gain informed consent from research participants, including for data archiving and sharing, and best practices for data anonymisation. I think that the guide comprehensively covers all relevant topics for data management in social sciences but it could be improved by giving more guidance on the use of qualitative data that is less structured than quantitative surveys.

➤ Across disciplines

The research institute where I work is very interdisciplinary, so when researchers ask me for help with data management and data analysis, they come from a wide range of areas and use different kinds of data. I wish there was a similar guide for researchers in the natural sciences and engineering.

➤ EOSC in practice.

I have not used any services from the European Open Science Cloud Portal yet but I received a voucher to test them so I would be interested in attending a training.

[Read Ana's story](#)

CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide User Story

Peter Čerče, Data Officer, Migrant Children and Communities in a Transforming Europe (MiCREATE) project, tells his story on using the guide for ethical challenges with interview data.

The researcher

I head the Centre for IT and Infrastructural Support to Research at the [Science and Research Centre Koper](#) as well as its Research Library. As a librarian, I am interested in the possibilities Open Access provides in managing research data. My daily tasks involve informing researchers and other data users about the concepts behind FAIR Data and how to make sure their data respects them.

The research project

The Horizon 2020 project Migrant Children and Communities in a Transforming Europe ([MiCREATE](#)) aims to gather their stories to support their needs and aspirations when it comes to integration. European countries and their education systems encounter many challenges due to ethnic, cultural, linguistic diversity, MiCREATE aims to:

- improve knowledge about children's experiences of life in new social environments
- explore school peer dynamics
- help teachers and educational staff to work with diversity
- develop child-centered tools for stimulating migrant integration
- design child-centered integration policy recommendations.

In the MiCREATE project, I am responsible for the Data Management Plan (DMP) and solving ethical issues in relation to Research Data Management (RDM). Ethical issues in data management are one of the main challenges in the MiCREATE project, as most of the qualitative research data will result from interviewing a particularly vulnerable group, namely migrant children.

My use of the CESSDA DMEG

For the MiCREATE data management plan (DMP), we consulted with (national) experts in the field. We met with the [Slovenian Social Science Data Archive](#), who directed us to the [CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide](#). We found the CESSDA Guide to be a very helpful tool, offering a wide variety of advice, tips, and examples from experts in the field.

In preparing the initial version of the MiCREATE DMP, we were using the [DMPonline tool](#), offered in the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide. The guide turned out to be very helpful for the consortium of fifteen partners from twelve different countries. The CESSDA DMEG directs you to European diversity issues in every step of the research data lifecycle.

I was particularly grateful for the way that the CESSDA DMEG is structured. It is fairly easy to find your way around, even though quantity of information can be intimidating. That said, Research Data Management in itself is such a vast field of expertise, that trying to find what you need in the enormous amount of information available online seems like mission impossible. That is why it is so helpful to have a guide like CESSDA's, which gathers information in one place, from an array of international experts.

Across disciplines

The Science and Research Centre Koper, where I work, consists of eight different research groups. Activities are predominantly based on interdisciplinary work, involving the humanities, social sciences and natural sciences. As much as the CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide is a helpful tool for general aspects of RDM, it would be particularly useful to have such exhaustive guides in other research fields as well.

EOSC in practice

I have been on the EOSC web portal and participated in only a few EOSC events.

I am definitely interested in attending training sessions on how to use EOSC services and tools. I hope to be more available in 2021.

CESSDA Data Management Expert Guide User Story

Duncan Simpson, a Marie Curie Fellow at the Institute of Social Sciences at the University of Lisbon, tells his story on using the guide for heterogeneous data collection.

The researcher

I'm Duncan Simpson, a Marie Curie Fellow at the Institute of Social Sciences (ICS) of the University of Lisbon. I gained my doctoral degree (PhD) from King's College London, with a thesis on the relations between the Catholic Church and the Salazar dictatorship.

About my research

My research project aims to challenge the existing historiographical narrative on the relation between ordinary citizens and the Salazarist political police (PIDE). The project will study the 'grey zone' of spontaneous interactions between common citizens and the political police, by highlighting the degree of social normalization of the PIDE, and by opening up new perspectives on the way power itself was exercised by the regime. Four research methodologies are used:

1. **State of the art and critical evaluation** of the relation between the historiography of the PIDE and 'anti-fascist' memory.
2. **Questionnaire-based opinion survey** directed to 400 participants in the cities of Lisbon, Viseu, Braga, and Faro.
3. **Oral history**: semi-directed interviews of 30 'ordinary citizens' with direct experience of life under the PIDE.
4. **Archival research**, focusing on the spontaneous interactions between individual citizens and the political police through letters of denunciation, petitions and letters of spontaneous application to join the PIDE.

My use of the CESSDA DMEG

I discovered the CESSDA DMEG thanks to the research methodology [workshop on data management planning organised at ICS](#) by Pedro Moura Ferreira and Patricia Miranda, on 6 November 2019. **For my research project** I used the following chapters:

- **Chapter 1 Plan**: A very useful introduction to Data Management Planning, allowing users to gain a clear knowledge of some of the key concepts in the area, such as FAIR Data.
- **Chapter 3 Process**: Particularly important in allowing users to grasp the methods needed to minimize errors during the processes of data entry and gain a practical knowledge of how best to manage the integrity and authenticity of the data during the whole of the research process
- **Chapter 4 Store**: Crucial in understanding and implementing adequate measures to protect the data against accidental loss and unauthorised manipulation, especially in relation to collecting sensitive personal data.

The benefits and impact of using the CESSDA DMEG were manifold and far-reaching. In collaboration with ICS's own Data Protection Officer, I was able to design a solid and secure DMP that was subsequently approved by the authorities of the Marie Curie Fellowship actions.

Across disciplines

Rather than across disciplines, the CESSDA DMEG helped me to plan my data management across different research methodologies. Where it proved to be particularly useful for the results of the large-scale opinion survey and the generation and treatment of data produced in the course of the oral history interviews.

EOOSC in practice

I have not used any services from the EOOSC portal. I do not currently feel that I need any training in these services and tools, though this may be the case later in my career.

[Read Duncan's story](#)

CESSDA DMEG[®]

User Stories

Showcasing the added value CESSDA DC[®] and CESSDA DMEG[®] for research addressing global challenges has proved to be illustrating for researchers and data experts. It allowed CESSDA[®] service providers to identify relevant datasets to highlight treasures from the wealth of datasets available. It also provided a great angle for the CESSDA DMEG[®] chapter highlighted.

Next steps will be undertaken to identify new user stories from the information that was provided by registrants to the 5 sessions of the CESSDA[®] roadshow.

With the document we provide Service Providers with a training and inspirational resource for the CESSDA DC[®] and CESSDA DMEG[®].
December 2021

 www.cessda.eu

 [@cessda_data](https://twitter.com/cessda_data)

 [company/cessda](https://www.linkedin.com/company/cessda)